
SOLVING CHRONIC VIBRATION PROBLEM ON 1475 HP MOTOR:

A CASE HISTORY

Ronny H Rusli and Faisal I Jamhoo

Predictive Maintenance Group, Aramco Riyadh Refinery, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

E-mail: ronny.rusli@aramco.com

Abstract:

A Diesel Hydro Treating Feed High Pressure pump, driven by 1475 HP motor has been reported experiencing high vibration since the past few years. The machine is equipped with two orthogonally mounted vibration proximity probes at each bearings. Furthermore, Bently Nevada System1 software available for diagnosing purposes. The problem came from one of motor's Non-Drive end probes that exits alarm limit at 63 μm and occasionally reaches trip level at 76 μm . Despite of several maintenance repairs in the past, yet it failed to improve the vibration behavior. This paper explains analysis and solutions performed that finally solve the problem. System1 optimization enhancement discussed, and Items for monitoring improvement proposed.

Keyword: Motor vibration; Rotor dynamic, Online Machinery Optimization

Background

A Diesel Hydro Treating Feed High Pressure pump's motor G0001B experienced high vibration from 2009 to 2013. The machine is equipped with two orthogonally mounted proximity probes at each bearing. The problem came from motor O/B, X location probe [1] that exits alarm limit at 63 μm and occasionally reaches trip level at 76 μm . The G0001B has never been undergone major overhaul since it was commissioned in 2001. Furthermore the machine was seems to be more acting as standby of G0001A.

Machine Setup

The analysis performed on 1475 HP motor tag# G0001A. The unit consists of motor and is direct coupled with pump. The schematic of the machine set consisting of 4 journal bearings is shown in Figure 1. Each bearing is equipped with orthogonally paired proximity vibration sensors.

Figure 1. Machine Setup

Observation

The vibration level of G0001B motor outboard (OB) X from 2006 till 2008 is found acceptable as can be seen on Figure 2 below. During this period, operation operated the unit more often. The problem seems to be started when the machine was operated after long on-standby mode from 2009 onward as can be seen on Figure 3.

Figure 2. Vibration trend motor side 2006-2008

Figure 3. Vibration trend motor side 2008-2012

The machine is connected to System1 which has function to record rotor dynamic behavior of the machine. However, it was noticed that System1 was not configured properly and does not acquire proper data during transient mode. Therefore, it was difficult to analysis further of the vibration behavior of the machine.

The decision then made to acquire vibration data of the machine by using eight channel data acquisition ADRE 208 direct to Bently 3500 monitor.

Furthermore, the data acquired by ADRE 208 revealed that the high vibration noticed on motor OB is real and not caused by instrumentation issue as suspected. This can be confirmed from vibration behavior during transient data that appears to be following the speed pattern (Figure 4).

The major vibration frequency found on motor OB is 1X frequency (Figure 5). This could mean that the majority of vibration was due to rotor force [2].

Orbit timebase plot appears to be in classic eight shape that could indicate sign of rubbing (Figure 6).

Shaft centerline plot shows that the rotor was properly lifted up from zero speed through operational speed. (Figure 7). This finding seems contrast with orbit timebase shape noticed above.

Figure 4 Data acquired during transient

Figure 5 Cascade behavior of the motor

Figure 6. Motor OB orbit timebase

Figure 7. Motor OB shaft centerline behavior

Recommendation

Based on data observed with ADRE above, then it was recommended as follows;

1. The major vibration frequencies of the motor were dominated by 1X RPM which indicate motor rotor problem [3] and need to be taken for balancing, run-out check, etc. However, it was observed that the motor equipped with external fan at the OB, therefore it was recommended to inspect the external fan, before going further to the shaft.
2. The classic eight shape of orbit timebase as discussed above seems to indicate rubbing. Even though, the evident was not supported by the look of shaft centerline plot, as a precaution it was also recommended to inspect motor OB bearing.

Findings

The recommendations were performed by maintenance, and the following evident found;

1. Mud found stacked on external fan blade (Figure 8 & 9). Furthermore, motor cooling tubes were found dirty covered by dust (Figure 10). Necessary action was then to thoroughly clean motor external fan and motor cooling tube.

Figure 8 Mud stacked on external fan blade

Figure 9 Mud stacked on external fan blade

Figure 10 Motor cooling tubes covered by dust

2. Motor bearing was found clean of any rubbing, radial clearance found was 0.0006", which is acceptable.

Current Z97-G0001B Condition

The G0001B was commissioned after recommended maintenance performed. It was found the vibration level on motor OB X probe position dramatically reduced from 80 μm to acceptable level 45 μm .

Reliability Improvement

The high vibration found on G0001B had led to several suggestions for improvement as follows;

1. It is important that all online Vibration Monitoring System (VMS) properly configured in order not to lose precious data. The data acquisition time needs to be set accordingly so that it will cover the ramping rate of a driver equipment.
- 2.
3. Proper switch-over between G0001A and G0001B plan need to be done by operation. It is recommended to operate/tested the standby machine at least in spillback mode every month, and avoid idle more than three months.
4. The present of mud/dust stacked on the impeller lead to a conclusion that additional task predictive maintenance (PM) may need to be done on this machine, and need to include cleaning the external and motor filter. However, this kind of task may not easily accessible for totally enclosed Air-to-Air cooled induction motor type like G0001B. Therefore, another alternative need to be explored, i.e to have self-cleaning filter technology to be installed on the motor. This self-cleaning filter technology can separate the dirty air from the main stream of clean air (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Self-cleaning filter technology.

Reference

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Author

Ronny H Rusli currently working as Predictive Maintenance Group Leader to lead Condition Monitoring Program at Aramco Riyadh facility, to ensure all rotating equipment availability by applying various condition monitoring techniques (vibration, oil analysis, etc). In the past, he worked as Field Service Engineer for SKF, managing Field Condition Monitoring Services at many plants, also has been adjusted in Rotor Dynamic analysis and in-situ balancing for turbo machinery when working as Machinery Diagnostics Engineer (MDS) for Bently Nevada representative. He has more than 20 years in Vibration Analysis.

Faisal I Jamhoor currently lead Reliability Unit at Riyadh Refinery. He has been more than 25 years dealing with Machinery Reliability Issues and Improvement.